

Effect of Serum Uric Acid Level on Outcome of Pregnancy in Pre-Eclampsia**Sanjan Das****Associate Professor, Department of OBG, MVJ Medical College and Research Hospital, Bangalore****Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024****Corresponding Author: Dr. Sanjan Das****Conflict of interest: Nil****Abstract:****Background:** Preeclampsia (PE) remains a significant contributor to both maternal and fetal death. According to available data, the prevalence of PE in developing countries is significantly elevated.**Aim:** The present study was designed to know the effect of serum uric acid level on outcome of pregnancy in PE patients.**Materials & methods:** A study was conducted at MVJ Medical College and Research Hospital department of OBG between the period of 1 year using a case-control design. A purposive sampling method was used to select 150 pregnant women in their third trimester. 60 individuals diagnosed with PE were chosen as cases, aged 18-35, while 60 healthy pregnant women were selected as controls, aged 18-36.**Results:** The study involved 80% of participants aged 21-30 years, with a mean standard deviation of 26.17±4.82 years and 25.79±4.13 years, respectively. The gestational age was 35.61±3.41 weeks and 35.9±3.06 weeks, respectively. Most participants were primiparous, with no significant difference. A significant proportion had irregular prenatal check-ups in both groups. Uric acid significantly raised after 28 weeks of gestation in PE women were observed to have intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) in our study than the PE women who had normal levels of uric acid after 28 weeks of gestation.**Conclusion:** High serum uric acid levels are linked to poor pregnancy outcomes in PE, including increased need for early birth and worse neonatal outcomes. Serum uric acid may be a significant prognostic marker in managing PE, but further large-scale investigations are needed to develop clinically applicable thresholds.**Keywords:** Preeclampsia; Maternal death; Fetal death; Pathophysiology; Developing countries; Uric acid; Endothelial dysfunction..

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Introduction

Preeclampsia (PE) remains a significant contributor to both maternal and fetal death. According to available data, the prevalence of PE in developing countries is significantly elevated, accounting for rural and urban areas of India was found to be nearly identical, with rates of 56.2% and 54% respectively. However, several states in India, namely Uttarakhand, Bihar, Jharkhand, and Kerala, exhibited higher rates above 70%, with Tripura having the highest prevalence at 87.5% [1].

PE continues to be perceived as a condition characterized by theories and a limited understanding of its pathophysiology [2]. However, it has been widely acknowledged that endothelial dysfunction plays a pivotal role in the pathogenesis of preeclampsia. Extensive research has been conducted to establish a distinctive screening test that can accurately predict the likelihood of having PE prior to the manifestation of typical symptoms [3-5]. There is currently no available screening test for PE that is both reliable and cost-effective. Serum

uric acid measurement is one of the most readily available and straightforward screening methodologies [6]. Multiple research investigations have provided evidence of a positive association between increased levels of uric acid in the maternal serum and negative outcomes for both the mother and the fetus [7]. The enzyme xanthine oxidase catalyzes the breakdown of purines, resulting in the production of uric acid. Uric acid concentrations are subject to various influences, including but not limited to a high protein diet, alcohol use, heightened cellular turnover, enzyme abnormalities in purine metabolism, and modified renal function.

In typical pregnant women, the quantity of uric acid in the serum initially decreases by 25-35% as a result of an increase in renal clearance caused by an elevated glomerular filtration rate (GFR) or a decrease in proximal tubular reabsorption due to alterations in its production rate. During the later stages of pregnancy, there is an observed increase in blood uric acid levels, which can be attributed to

factors such as heightened fetal production, reduced binding to albumin, and a decline in uric acid clearance. This trend persists until the end of pregnancy, culminating in a return to pre-pregnancy levels [8]. There exist multiple potential sources for elevated levels of uric acid in individuals with PE. Renal dysfunction, heightened tissue degradation, elevated oxidative stress, and augmented xanthine oxidase activity typically serve as secondary factors contributing to this condition [9]. The renal system is responsible for the filtration, reabsorption, and secretion of uric acid [10]. The prevailing hypothesis for hyperuricemia in PE is attributed to heightened reabsorption and diminished excretion of uric acid [11].

Uric acid possesses the capacity to induce inflammation, oxidative stress, and endothelial dysfunction, hence potentially contributing to the development of hypertension, vascular disease, and renal disease. An elevated amount of serum uric acid is indicative of the presence of underlying oxidative stress. Elevated levels of oxidative stress and the generation of Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) have been suggested as an additional factor contributing to the observed hyperuricemia in PE, in addition to renal impairment [11]. Uric acid exhibits great efficacy as a modulator of inflammatory processes. Uric acid elicits the activation of monocytes, leading to the synthesis of pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β and IL-17 [11,12]. There exists a positive correlation between the elevated levels of circulating TNF- κ and circulating uric acid in women diagnosed with preeclampsia [12]. The examination of a composite biochemical indicator, specifically indicators associated with vascular dysfunction, such as elevated levels of uric acid, has the potential to enhance our capacity to forecast and prevent PE in the near future [13,14]. Therefore, the present study was designed to know the effect of serum uric acid level on the outcome of pregnancy in PE patients.

Materials & Methods:

A study employing a case-control design was carried out at the Department of XXXXXXXX, MVJ Medical College and Research Hospital, spanning from 1 year. A purposive sampling method was employed to choose a sample of 150 pregnant women in their third trimester of pregnancy who were attending the Obstetrics and Gynecology department of MVJ Medical College and Research Hospital. Out of the whole sample, 60 individuals

diagnosed with PE were chosen as cases, falling within the age range of 18-35 years. Additionally, 60 pregnant women of normal healthy age were selected as controls, with ages ranging from 18-36 years. Through a comprehensive evaluation of their medical history, physical examination, and pertinent laboratory investigations, pregnant women who had pre-existing hypertension, diabetes mellitus, or renal illness were excluded from the study. Following the acquisition of informed written consent from all participants in the study, pertinent data were recorded in a predetermined data sheet. Additionally, strict aseptic precautions were followed to ensure the collection of blood samples from all participants. These samples were then utilized to estimate the concentration of serum uric acid. The estimation of serum uric acid level was conducted using a colorimetric technique.

Statistical analysis:

The statistical analysis was conducted using version 14 of the Statistical Package for Social Science for Windows computer software. The study employed Student's unpaired t' test to compare the mean values of several parameters in order to identify any differences between two groups. A chi-square test was conducted to determine the statistical significance of the difference in gravida distribution between the groups. A significant level of ≤ 0.05 was deemed the minimum threshold for any statistical analysis.

Results:

Many participants in the study fell within the age range of 21-30 years (case 80%, control 88%). The mean standard deviation (SD) of age between the case and control groups was found to be 26.17 \pm 4.82 years and 25.79 \pm 4.13 years, respectively. The observed change did not reach statistical significance ($p > 0.05$).

Figures 1 & 2 present the baseline parameters pertaining to gestational age, gravida, and antenatal check-up outcomes. The mean and standard deviation of gestational age in the case and control groups were 35.61 \pm 3.41 weeks and 35.9 \pm 3.06 weeks, respectively. Conversely, a majority of the participants were primiparous in both the case and control groups. There was no significant difference seen between the two parameters ($p > 0.05$). A significant proportion of participants in both groups had irregular prenatal check-ups.

Figure 1: Gestational age (in weeks) of the study cohort

Figure 2: Gravid and antenatal check-up status of the study cohort

Figure 3 presents a comparative analysis of serum uric acid levels between the patients and controls. The mean and standard deviation (SD) serum uric acid levels in the cases and controls were 7.81 ± 1.56 mg/dl and 5.13 ± 1.42 mg/dl, respectively. The observed level exhibited a statistically significant increase in cases compared to controls ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 3: Uric acid levels in the study cohorts

We screened all the PE women and the control women at 10 weeks for uric acid as a baseline concentration. Again after 28 weeks of gestation period, we estimated the uric acid levels to all the women of the study cohort. Interestingly we

observed a significant raise of uric acid in 21 PE women out of 60 cases in whom were observed to have intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) in our study than the PE women who had normal levels of uric acid after 28 weeks of gestation (figure 4).

Figure 4: Uric acid levels in the PE women group

Discussion:

The goal of the study was to determine the relationship between serum uric acid and PE. The present study found no statistically significant difference between the two groups in terms of maternal age and gestational age. Maternal age.

According to the study, the incidence of preeclampsia was high in primigravid. A similar conclusion was drawn by Aksornphusitaphong et al., [15] where they showed nulliparity as a risk factor for preeclampsia. The maximum number of cases and controls received irregular antenatal checkups. According to the study, preeclamptic patients have a lower frequency of regular antenatal

check-ups than normal pregnant women. Hyperuricemia is a common finding in preeclamptic pregnancies, evident from early pregnancy. In the early research long back, researchers first noted elevated serum uric acid concentrations in preeclamptic women. Since that time, numerous reports have demonstrated a relationship between uric acid concentration and the severity of the diseases [16]. With increasing uric acid concentration, the severity of PE increases [5-11]. Hyperuricemia is considered a risk factor for hypertension, cardiovascular disease, and renal disease, but the role of uric acid in the pathophysiology of PE is still not well understood. While this concept is largely unstudied, we expand

upon ideas forwarded by a study [17] to share in the hypothesis that an elevated concentration of uric acid in preeclamptic women is not simply a marker of disease severity but rather contributes directly to the pathogenesis of disorder.

In the present study, we have found that mean serum uric acid concentrations were significantly higher in preeclamptic women than normal pregnant women. A favourable number of studies done previously had revealed similar findings [1,4,6]. However, several other studies showed that serum uric acid is a poor predictor of PE [18,19]. The development of methods to predict and prevent PE complications in early pregnancy is important for the management of PE complications. Interestingly our findings revealed that when the (IUGR) is associated with PE, uric acid levels increased after 28 weeks of pregnancy.

Therefore, these results may support the hypothesis that the rise of uric acid levels is linked to maternal endothelial dysfunction and exacerbated systemic inflammatory response in preeclampsia [20]. In this regard, we propose that monitoring uric acid levels during pregnancy, in combination with biochemical and ultrasonographic markers, could enable a better diagnosis of these disorders. Hyperuricemia is one of the earliest and most consistent observations in preeclamptic pregnancies. Although not all women with PE exhibit elevated circulating uric acid concentrations, they seem to identify a subset of PE women who are more susceptible to maternal and fetal mortality. As a result, measuring serum uric acid concentration appears to be a useful test for predicting maternal complications in the management of women with preeclampsia.

Conclusion:

According to this study, high serum uric acid levels are associated with poor pregnancy outcomes in PE, and the need for an early birth was even more common in mothers whose serum uric acid levels were higher. There was a correlation between greater levels and worse neonatal outcomes, such as lower birth weight [21], more preterm births, and more admissions to the neonatal critical care unit. By helping to identify high-risk pregnancies that may require closer monitoring and timely interventions, serum uric acid may be a significant prognostic marker in the management of preeclampsia. To clarify the processes and develop clinically applicable standardized uric acid thresholds, additional large-scale investigations are required.

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